

PREDICTION OF AUTOCLAVE CURING OF AERONAUTICAL COMPOSITES PARTS AND OF RESULTING SPRING-IN THROUGH ESI COMPOSITES SIMULATION SOLUTION

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Keywords: composite distortion, autoclave simulation, curing, Finite elements, CFD

ABSTRACT

Composite materials based on thermoset matrix are commonly used for manufacturing of aeronautics structures. These materials require after draping a polymerization in an autoclave. The curing stage done under controlled atmosphere induces internal stresses and geometrical distortions that can conduct to the part rejection.

This paper presents end to end simulation that takes into account the influence of the autoclave process and material phase evolution during curing on the quality of the final part.

The analysis is done in 2 phases: the first phase is a fluid dynamics analysis used to simulate gas flow and thermal exchange in the autoclave. The second phase is a thermo-chemical mechanical analysis where geometrical deformations and residual stresses are computed.

Thermal history of a composite part during its autoclave cycle will depend on many parameters like, gas flow velocity and gas temperature evolution, autoclave loading, thermal response of the tooling and exothermy of the reaction. Results of this first step simulation will be to generate an accurate thermal field history and degree of cure history in the composite part taking into accounts all these effects.

During curing step, generation of geometric distortions and residual stresses are directly linked to material thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage due to cross linking reaction. A biphasic model [1] is used which takes into account the change in material state (from rubbery to glassy) during the curing step. Material evolution is then used to compute expansional strains which can lead to residual stresses and shape distortion.

Results obtained with ESI composites simulation solution will then be compared to different cases manufactured using aeronautic process from SAMC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoset prepreg composites are intensively used in the aerospace industry due to their low weight and high performance characteristics. Their forming process allows flexibility in the product shape and is a one step process. Consolidation use autoclave process which is a pressured vessel that applies both pressure and temperature cycles to the composite parts placed inside. The pressure applied to the composites parts lead to high compaction composites parts with higher performance.

Currently, the autoclave process is the most widely used and also the most mature process for the manufacturing of composite part. More than 50% of the composite parts are manufactured by autoclave, and up to 80% in the aerospace field. The quality control of the autoclave process and its improvement is mainly based on tests that take a long time and involve high costs. In addition, because of the limited number of tests, it is difficult to know the various factors that govern the quality of the product.

During autoclave curing, internal stresses are developed in the composites part. These stresses generate shape distortion following the release of the part from the mold. The known factors responsible for the internal stresses are the thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage of the thermoset resin which occurs during the transformation from liquid to solid state.

The precision of the distortion simulation is directly linked to the accuracy of the applied thermal field history. Numerical simulation of the autoclave process and associated distortion prediction is a high scientific level technology which involves many physics and difficulties.

The work presented in this document concerns the definition of a global simulation chain which allows taking into account autoclave process effect on the geometric distortion and residual stresses occurrence in order to anticipate the risk at the initial design stage.

2 AUTOCLAVE SIMULATION

The first purpose of autoclave simulation is to predict the real temperature field inside the autoclave so as to get more realistic temperature and curing boundary conditions for the distortion analysis and thus more accurate part distortion prediction.

The second purpose of autoclave simulation is to optimize its heating power, pressure and loading (positioning of the part inside the cavity, loading of several parts, relative positioning) by looking at resulting temperature distribution within the part and avoiding temperature peaks and non-uniformities.

2.1 CFD analysis: gas flow, heat transfer and curing

The autoclave is a device that can generate a controlled pressure and temperature environment. Composite part curing is achieved by means of air that is heated inside the equipment through different type of thermal exchanger. An electric fan puts the indoor air into motion, and the forced circulation allows setting a homogeneous temperature field inside the autoclave. The cooling process is achieved by means of circulating cold water, or cooling fluids, through a specific exchanger, that allows, the equipment indoor temperature to be reduced down to the required values.

Model used by SAMC has some differences from standard autoclave system. Conventional autoclaves (Fig. 2) have a radial duct that is used to transfer air from the rear of the autoclave to the front. Model considered (Fig. 1) uses the floor as the forward air delivery system. Additionally H-Slot flow adjustment panels are used to straighten and balance air flow in the autoclave. With this system poor air flow region are reduced, full volume is useable.

Figure 1: SAMC's Autoclave

Figure 2: Conventional Autoclave

CFD analyses are performed using CFD-ACE+ software from ESI Group. CFD-ACE+ is a set of computer applications for multi-physics computational analysis using finite volume technic. The programs provide an integrated geometry and grid generation software, a graphical user interface for preparing the model, a computational solver for performing the simulation, and interactive visualization software for examining and analyzing the simulation results.

Different analyses were performed with an increasing degree of complexity starting from the simulation of the empty autoclave to the full curing simulation of the composite part.

Starting from the CAD definition provided by SAMC (Fig. 3), a grid mesh was generated for the empty autoclave (Fig. 4).

Figure 3: Internal view of the Autoclave CAD model Figure 4: Mesh section of the corresponding CFD grid

In this model cool down is supposed sufficiently low and can be manage by heater power reduction and by temperature loss due to convection with external environment. Flow, Heat transfer, curing and turbulence models are involved during autoclave simulation. Pressure was considered constant during the curing cycle.

In order to decrease CPU time needed to solve such kind of problem, 2 steps strategy was defined. A first steady state flow analysis is performed assuming constant fan rotation. Starting from this stationary flow a second step of heat conduction analysis is then performed based on the heat power evolution.

Activating the Flow module implies the solution of the velocity field by solving for the x-, y-, and z-momentum equations and the pressure field by solving the pressure correction equation. A laminar flow is assumed unless the turbulence module k- ϵ is activated (around flow stabilizer fan system, tooling).

The governing equations for the Flow model represent mathematical statements of the conservation laws of physics for flow:

- The mass of a fluid is conserved; that is, there is no loss or gain of mass in the system.
- The time rate of change of momentum equals the sum of the forces on the fluid (Newton's second law).

CFD-ACE+ uses these two laws to develop a set of equations, known as the Navier-Stokes equations, to solve numerically using an iterative method.

The Heat Transfer Module performs heat transfer analysis and implies the resolution of the total enthalpy form of the energy equation. In order to decrease model complexity and CPU time, only fluid volumes, tooling and composite volume area were considered. Due to the small thickness of the tooling support, conduction gradient effect was not considered.

3 types of boundary conditions are considered in this model: Thin wall condition for the platform and the fan shroud (no momentum transport across a thin-wall); Adiabatic wall condition (no heat flux) for autoclave external shell, table top and flow stabilizer area; External heat transfer (Convection) is associated with autoclave left and right side.

2.2 CFD analysis: Empty autoclave simulation

Autoclave process is piloted by 2 parameters: temperature cycle (Tini from Figure Fig. 5) and pressure cycle. Using these 2 parameters and different thermal sensor localized in the internal chamber, heat power, cooling power and fan speed are automatically adjust in order to reach targeted temperature values. Air properties were used for flow and heat analysis. Experimental measurements were performed by SAMC.

Figure 5 Imposed (Tini), measured (TC2), computed (T2) temperature cycle in central part of the autoclave

Constant fan speed was considered and only heat power was adjust in order to reach imposed temperature cycle. Difference in term of thermal response (Fig. 5) could be explained by a lower fan speed and air conduction coefficient than in reality.

Figure 6 Velocity field at the end of the steady state

Figure 7 Temperature field $t=15000s$

Due to heater position, air flow is compressed and generates locally higher velocity (Fig.6). After flow stabilizer, velocity field is quite low and homogeneous. This homogeneity could be found also in terms of thermal response in the working area of the autoclave. As explained in the autoclave description, flow stabilizer function is to straighten the velocity field in order to homogenize the temperature.

2.3 Air flow and Temperature field analysis

Different configurations were considered in order to investigate thermal field history variation around composites parts during curing process and its effect on distortion. Geometries considered were:

- Thin and thick plates (Fig.8),
- C spar with different tooling position in the autoclave chamber (Fig. 9, Fig. 10),
- T stiffened panel obtained by co-curing and co-bonding process,
- Full industrial 3m long C spar.

Figure 8: Temperature field at the end of the curing cycle just before cool down (Thin and thick plates curing).

A comparison is proposed Figure 10 between 2 configurations of the autoclave loading. In the first configuration tooling is aligned to the air flow and is perpendicular in the second one. As first results, Figures 10 show a modification of the temperature field over part surfaces due to the generation of flow perturbation around the tooling. Next step will be to transfer this information to the distortion module in order to quantify the effect in terms of geometrical distortion and residual stresses.

Figure 9 Tooling definition and associated meshing (green part: composite C spar)

Figure 10a Temperature field and velocity direction (Tooling align to the air flow)

Figure 10b Temperature field and velocity direction (Tooling perpendicular to the air flow)

3 DISTORTION SIMULATION

Distortion analysis is based on the element formulation from Svanberg [1] which propose a non-coupled thermo-chemical and mechanical transitory analysis. This model was implemented in PAM-DISTORTION from ESI Group into an orthotropic homogeneous solid element formulation. Results used as input for the computation of geometrical distortion and residual stresses are the temperature and degree of cure history coming from PAM-RTM curing analysis or CFD-ACE+ autoclave simulation. Using these local information, T_g evolution is computed from Di Benedetto equation and different material phase could be defined: liquid when $\chi < \chi_{gel}$, Rubbery when $T > T_g$ and $\chi > \chi_{gel}$ and Glassy when $T < T_g$. During curing, material properties will change from Rubbery to Glassy and expansional strain will evolve in function of chemical shrinkage and thermal expansion.

3.1 Distortion model

The model proposed by Svanberg is an incremental constitutive model based on linear viscoelasticity, but with the rate dependence replaced by a path dependence on the states variables, ε_{kl} , T and χ .

$$S_{ij}^l(t + \Delta t) = \begin{cases} 0 & , T \geq T_g(\chi) \\ S_{ij}^l(t) + (C_{ijkl}^E - C_{ijkl}^r) \cdot \Delta(\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^E) & , T < T_g(\chi) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{ij} = \begin{cases} C_{ijkl}^r \cdot \Delta(\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^E) - S_{ij}^l(t) & , T \geq T_g(\chi) \\ C_{ijkl}^E \cdot \Delta(\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^E) & , T < T_g(\chi) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

T : Temperature,
 χ : Degree of cure,
 ε_{kl} : Cauchy infinitesimal strain tensor,
 C_{ijkl}^E and C_{ijkl}^F : glassy and rebury modulus tensor.

As we can see, the mechanical properties are dependent to material state. Composite material is in Rubbery state when the temperature is above the glass transition temperature and in the glassy state when the temperature is below. For a thermoset resin T_g is related to degree of cure χ . A common expression is the DiBenedetto equation.

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda \cdot \chi}{1 - (1 - \lambda) \cdot \chi} \quad (3)$$

T_{g0} : glass transition temperature of the uncured system ($\chi=0$)
 $T_{g\infty}$: glass transition temperature of the fully cured system ($\chi=1$)
 λ : Material constant

This formulation has some requirements:

- the material is linear elastic in both glassy and rubbery states; neither the glassy nor the rubbery stiffness depends on temperature or degree of cure,
- heating through the glass-rubber transition is fast enough and cooling through the rubber-glass transition slow enough to exclude explicit time dependence.

To complete this formulation expansional strains are express as below:

$$\varepsilon_{kl}^E(t + \Delta t) = \varepsilon_{kl}^E(t) + \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^E \quad (4)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^E &= \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^T + \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^C \\ \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^T &= \alpha_{kl} \cdot \Delta T \\ \Delta \varepsilon_{kl}^C &= \beta_{kl} \cdot \Delta \chi \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

ΔT and $\Delta \chi$ represent temperature and degree of cure increment over the time step,
 ε_{kl}^T : Thermal expansion tensor,
 ε_{kl}^C : Chemical shrinkage strains tensor.

3.2 Distortion simulation

Simulations were performed in order to investigate the influence of different effects on distortion:

- no symmetry of the laminate stack,
- relaxation after trimming,
- temperature field modification due to autoclave loading modification,
- co-curing and co-bonding process,
- Interaction with tooling: expansion, separation.

Each simulation use as input on each element, a temperature history and degree of cure history coming from thermal and curing analysis (i.e. for example from autoclave simulation). Using this information, it's possible to compute T_g evolution and to define the different phase of the material (Fig. 11).

Figure 11 Material phase modification during curing cycle in the central part of the C spar.

Next step is to define the evolution of the boundary conditions during the manufacturing process. For example, the C spar is fixed to the mold on his inner face during all the curing process. At the end of the temperature cycle, just after the cool down the part is released from the mold, trimmed and positioned on a reference plane for distortion measurement. Isostatic boundaries are defined on this plane and geometric distortions coming from expansional strain are computed and compared to experimental values with a good agreement (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Displacement comparison along Y direction (spring-in): simulation (left picture) versus experimental (green line: right picture)

9 CONCLUSIONS

Work proposed in this document concerns the simulation of the autoclave process and the analysis of resulting distortion. Autoclave air flow evolution was investigated using CFD analysis and distortion using a thermo-chemical mechanical model from PAM-DISTORTION. First simulation results have shown the influence of the autoclave loading onto the thermal field history received by the composite part and a good agreement with experimental distortion measurements. This thermal history will affect the evolution of degree of cure and the phase change of the matrix. Other parameters are investigated in this project in order to complete the analysis on the influencing parameters. Using these results it should be possible to define basic guidelines for the autoclave loading and to minimize distortion.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to these results has received funding from BPI France N°A1207028 Q and “International Science & Technology Cooperation Program of China” N°2013DFG52420.

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